

Advantages of implemented System

1. Distribution of electricity will be smoother, due to faster decision making in case of a crisis situation.
2. The prim's algorithm to find a minimum spanning tree, is more than any other greedy algorithm.
3. The time required for computation using a prim's algorithm is very less, as compared to other system.

Prim's Algorithm:

Fig. 2. Structure of a prim's algorithm

Flowchart

Fig.3. Flow chart for sequence of operation

Simulation Results

Simulation of proposed system is ben done by using a python software to implement code for the architecture proposed in fig.1. The python program is written in such a manner that it should check every possibility of failure of architecture.Simulation result is carried out by PYTHON 2.7.10.

CASE A: Show all links present in the Grid

In case of 0 link cost between power supply for the minimizing the prim's calculating cost in program that cannot effect minimum spanning tree cost.

```
Python 2.7.10 Shell
Python 2.7.10 (default, May 23 2015, 09:41:32) [MC w-1500 32 bit (Intel)] on win32
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> ===== RESTART =====
>>>
Select The Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
?
2016-02-09 08:34:20

Edges Present in the Smart Grid System:

(EDC I, EDC II, 0, 101)
(EDC II, EDC III, 0, 102)
(EDC I, EDC III, 0, 103)
(EDC I, A, 2, 104)
(EDC I, B, 2, 105)
(EDC I, C, 2, 106)
(EDC II, E, 2, 107)
(EDC II, F, 2, 108)
(EDC III, G, 2, 109)
(EDC III, H, 2, 110)
(A, 0, 2, 111)
(A, B, 2, 112)
(B, C, 2, 113)
(C, D, 2, 114)
(D, E, 2, 115)
(E, F, 2, 116)
(F, G, 2, 117)
(G, H, 2, 118)
(H, I, 2, 119)
(I, J, 2, 120)
(J, K, 2, 121)
(K, L, 2, 122)
```

Fig. 4. Show all links present in the Grid

CASE B: Smart Grid

In this section we formulate the prim's algorithm in the python code using python 2.7.10.Using prim's code we can find out the minimum spanning tree cost for giving system having two power supply and 12 user node that can connect through link provided on the basis of the link cost between the system.

```
Python 2.7.10 Shell
Python 2.7.10 (default, May 23 2015, 09:41:32) [MC w-1500 32 bit (Intel)] on win32
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> ===== RESTART =====
>>>
Select The Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
?
2016-02-09 08:35:19

Node EDC I and EDC II connected with cost: 0 Link Code: 101
Node EDC I and EDC III connected with cost: 0 Link Code: 102
Node EDC I and D connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 103
Node EDC I and A connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 104
Node EDC I and G connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 105
Node EDC II and E connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 107
Node EDC II and B connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 108
Node EDC III and C connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 109
Node EDC III and F connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 110
Node EDC III and H connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 111
Node G and I connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 111
Node G and J connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 120
Node H and K connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 121
Node H and L connected with cost: 2 Link Code: 122

Select The Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
```

Fig.5. Smart Grid

CASE C: Add new link to the Grid

If there is a chance of adding a new link into the grid because of the some natural or manmade issues that could result into adding new link into system that can cause the increase the redundancy in the system We can add the link in the system easily and add the parameter into the system to calculate and reformulate the new spanning tree for the system.

```
Python 2.7.10 Shell
File Edit Shell Debug Options Window Help
Python 2.7.10 (default, May 23 2015, 09:40:32) [MSC v.1500 32 bit (Intel)] on win32
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> ===== RESTART =====
>>>
Select the Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
'!'
2016-02-03 08:17:04

Preparing for adding new Link into Smart Grid Family:

Enter the first node: '500 1'
Enter the second node: '50'
Enter Link Cost: 3
Enter Link Cost: '120'
New link added to family.....
Select the Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
```

Fig.6. Add new link to the Grid

CASE D: Remove the link from the Grid

By the chance there is also a possibility of the system to remove the existing link from the grid system because of frequent failure in that link that could result into decrease the efficiency of the system. So that we can remove an existing system link and recalculate the prim's cost.

```
Python 2.7.10 Shell
File Edit Shell Debug Options Window Help
Python 2.7.10 (default, May 23 2015, 09:40:32) [MSC v.1500 32 bit (Intel)] on win32
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> ===== RESTART =====
>>>
Select the Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
'!'
2016-02-03 08:18:45

Preparing for Removing old Link from Smart Grid Family:

Enter the first node: '50'
Enter the second node: '1'
Enter Link Cost: 2
Enter Link Cost: '120'
Entered Link Removed from family.....
Select the Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
```

Fig.7. Remove the link from the Grid

CASE E: Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost.

In this case we just get to know the total prim's cost for the get the knowledge of prim's algorithm efficiency.

```
Python 2.7.10 Shell
File Edit Shell Debug Options Window Help
Python 2.7.10 (default, May 23 2015, 09:40:32) [MSC v.1500 32 bit (Intel)] on win32
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> ===== RESTART =====
>>>
Select the Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
'!'
2016-02-03 08:19:34

Preparing for Calculating Minimum Spanning Tree Cost:

Network is connected with cost: 24

Select the Operation >
1) Show all link in present Grid
2) Smart Grid
3) Add new link to Grid
4) Remove Link From Network
5) Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost
```

Fig.8. Find Minimum Spanning Tree Cost.

Conclusion:

The system implemented is proposed architecture for self healing smart grid system, using minimum spanning tree cost of the prim's algorithm. The advantages of prim's algorithm is used to implement self healing property of smart grid. By finding a minimum spanning tree cost the smart grids will be less vulnerable to faults and efficiency of the system can be maximized by reducing the outages and by doing a proper contingency analysis. By implementation of the proposed system we can find the which link to be removed for satisfactory operation of the distribution network.

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